

Bounded composition operators on de Branges-Rovnyak spaces

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Abstract

We study bounded composition operators acting on de Branges–Rovnyak spaces from the viewpoint of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. Using kernel domination and Schur product techniques, we obtain sufficient conditions for the boundedness of composition operators between de Branges–Rovnyak spaces. This kernel-based approach also extends naturally to weighted composition operators, yielding boundedness results that generalize known results for model spaces and recover earlier work as special cases.

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1 Introduction

Let \mathbb{D} and \mathbb{T} be the unit disk and the unit circle in the complex plane respectively. The Hardy space H^2 is the Hilbert space of analytic functions f on \mathbb{D} for which the norm

$$\|f\|^2 = \sup_{0 \leq r < 1} \int_{\mathbb{T}} |f(rz)|^2 dm(z)$$

is finite. Let H^∞ denote the space of bounded analytic functions on \mathbb{D} , and let \mathcal{S} denote the closed unit ball in H^∞ , that is, we set

$$\mathcal{S} = \left\{ u \in H^\infty : \|u\|_\infty = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} |u(z)| \leq 1 \right\}.$$

This is called the Schur class. For a function φ in L^∞ , the Toeplitz operator T_φ on H^2 with symbol φ is defined by $T_\varphi f = P(\varphi f)$, where P is the orthogonal projection from L^2 onto H^2 .

We consider Hilbert spaces called operator ranges, defined as follows. Let A be a bounded operator on a Hilbert space H . We define the operator range $\mathcal{M}(A) = AH$ equipped with the inner product

$$\langle Af, Ag \rangle_{\mathcal{M}(A)} = \langle f, g \rangle_H \quad f, g \in H \ominus \text{Ker } A.$$

Given a nonconstant function u in \mathcal{S} , the de Branges-Rovnyak space $\mathcal{H}(u)$ is defined by the operator range $\mathcal{M}((I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2})$. We see that $\mathcal{H}(u)$ is a reproducing kernel Hilbert space on \mathbb{D} with kernel

$$k_w^u(z) = \frac{1 - \overline{u(w)}u(z)}{1 - \bar{w}z}.$$

If u is an inner function, then $\mathcal{H}(u)$ coincides with the model space $K_u = H^2 \ominus uH^2$. Thus de Branges-Rovnyak spaces provide a natural generalization of model spaces while retaining a rich reproducing kernel structure [8, 1].

Given an analytic self-map φ of \mathbb{D} , the composition operator C_φ is defined by $C_\varphi f = f \circ \varphi$. From the Littlewood subordination principle, we see that the composition operator C_φ on H^2 is bounded. Many mathematicians study composition operators on various function spaces. Let us focus on the composition operators on Hilbert spaces inside the Hardy space H^2 , such as model spaces and de Branges-Rovnyak spaces. In [3, 6], we study several boundedness and compactness results for composition operators on model spaces. For example, let φ and u be inner functions. Then $z(u \circ \varphi)$ is also an inner function and the composition operator

$$C_\varphi : \mathcal{K}_u \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_{z(u \circ \varphi)}$$

is well-defined and bounded. Notable progress in this direction was made by Jury. In [5], for de Branges-Rovnyak spaces most existing works focus on compactness or norm estimates, and general sufficient conditions for boundedness remain relatively limited. In [2], the compact composition operators on the de Branges-Rovnyak spaces are studied using reproducing kernel techniques. On the other hand, little has been reported on the sufficient conditions for the boundedness of composition operators on de Branges-Rovnyak spaces. The purpose of this paper is to further develop a kernel-based approach to bounded composition operators on de Branges-Rovnyak spaces, motivated by recent work on composition and weighted composition operators in reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. Our main results provide sufficient conditions for the boundedness of composition operators between de Branges-Rovnyak spaces, formulated in terms of domination relations between the associated reproducing kernels. The key tool is the Schur product theorem, which allows us to compare kernels in a flexible and transparent manner. This viewpoint extends earlier results for model spaces (for example, [3, Section 6]) and places them into a unified framework.

As an application of this approach, we also study weighted composition operators of the form $W_{\psi, \varphi} f = \psi \cdot (f \circ \varphi)$, where $\psi \in H^\infty$. From the reproducing kernel perspective, such operators naturally combine a pullback with a Schur multiplication. This observation allows us to derive boundedness results for weighted composition operators that generalize known results and recover the unweighted case as a special instance.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we study inclusions of some reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. In Section 3, we study Hilbert spaces inside H^2 such as operator ranges including de Branges-Rovnyak spaces. In Section 4, we state our main results, that is, boundedness of the composition operators on some de Branges-Rovnyak spaces. In Section 5, we study weighted composition operators as an application.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we present inclusions of some reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. As can be seen from [7, Section 5], these inclusions play an important role in studying composition operators. Before stating the theorems, we recall the definitions and properties of positive matrices and kernel functions. Our reference is [7].

- Definition 1.** (i) Let $A = (a_{ij})$ be an $n \times n$ complex matrix. Then A is positive (written $A \geq 0$) if and only if for every $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n \in \mathbb{C}$ we have $\sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i \bar{\alpha}_j a_{ij} \geq 0$.
- (ii) Let X be a set and let $K : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a function of two variables. Then K is called a kernel function (written $K \geq 0$) provided that for every n and for every choice of n distinct points, $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq X$, the matrix is positive, i. e., $(K(x_i, x_j)) \geq 0$.

Let $A = (a_{ij})$ and $B = (b_{ij})$ be two $n \times n$ matrices. Then their Schur product is defined to be the $n \times n$ matrix $A * B = (a_{ij} b_{ij})$. Theorem 2, known as the Schur product theorem, states that the Schur product of positive semidefinite matrices is also positive semi-definite.

Theorem 2 (Schur product). Let $P = (p_{ij})$ and $Q = (q_{ij})$ be two $n \times n$ matrices. If $P \geq 0$ and $Q \geq 0$, then $P * Q \geq 0$.

The inequality $A \geq B$ means that $A - B$ is positive semi-definite. We will see that the Schur product preserves this inequality.

Proposition 3 ([7]). Let $A = (a_{ij}), B = (b_{ij}), P = (p_{ij})$ and $Q = (q_{ij})$ be $n \times n$ matrices. If $A \geq P \geq 0$ and $B \geq Q \geq 0$, then $A * B \geq P * Q \geq 0$.

Proof. From the assumption, we note that $A - P = (a_{ij} - p_{ij})$ and $B - Q = (b_{ij} - q_{ij})$ are positive semi-definite. For any positive integer n and every $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n \in \mathbb{C}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} A * B - P * Q &= \sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i \bar{\alpha}_j (a_{ij} b_{ij} - p_{ij} q_{ij}) \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i \bar{\alpha}_j (a_{ij} b_{ij} - a_{ij} q_{ij} + a_{ij} q_{ij} - p_{ij} q_{ij}) \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i \bar{\alpha}_j a_{ij} (b_{ij} - q_{ij}) + \sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i \bar{\alpha}_j (a_{ij} - p_{ij}) q_{ij}. \end{aligned}$$

From the Schur product theorem, each sum is positive semi-definite. This implies that $A * B - P * Q \geq 0$. Hence we obtain the conclusion. \square

Next, we consider inclusions of some reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. We state Aronszajn's inclusion theorem without proof.

Theorem 4 (Aronszajn). *Let X be a set and let $K_i : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2$ be positive kernel function with corresponding reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces $H(K_i)$ and the norm $\|\cdot\|_i, i = 1, 2$. Then $H(K_1) \subset H(K_2)$ if and only if there exists some constant $c > 0$ such that $K_1(x, y) \leq c^2 K_2(x, y)$. Moreover, in this case, $\|f\|_2 \leq c\|f\|_1$ for all $f \in H(K_1)$.*

In [7, Section 5.7], multipliers on a reproducing kernel Hilbert space are defined and characterized.

Definition 5 ([7]). *Let H_1 and H_2 be reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces on the same set X and K_1 and K_2 denote their kernel functions, respectively. A function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is called a multiplier of H_1 into H_2 provided that $fH_1 := \{fh : h \in H_1\} \subseteq H_2$. We let $\mathcal{M}(H_1, H_2)$ denote the set of all multipliers of H_1 into H_2 .*

Theorem 6 ([7]). *Let H_1 and H_2 be reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces on the same set X with kernel functions K_1 and K_2 , respectively. The following are equivalent:*

- (i) $f \in \mathcal{M}(H_1, H_2)$;
- (ii) $f \in \mathcal{M}(H_1, H_2)$ and multiplication operator M_f is bounded operator;
- (iii) there exists some constant $c \geq 0$ such that $f(x)K_1(x, y)\overline{f(y)} \leq c^2 K_2(x, y)$.

Now we introduce the product of the kernels. We call $K(x, y) = K_1(x, y)K_2(x, y)$ the product of the kernels and we denote it by $K = K_1 \odot K_2$. More precisely, let $K_1 \otimes K_2$ be the tensor product of the kernels K_1 and K_2 . Let $\Delta : X \rightarrow X \times X$ denote the diagonal map, defined by $\Delta(x) = (x, x)$. Then $K_1 \odot K_2(x, y) = K_1 \otimes K_2(\Delta(x), \Delta(y))$, that is, $K_1 \odot K_2 = (K_1 \otimes K_2) \circ \Delta$. We note that $K_1 \odot K_2$ is a kernel function from Theorem 2. Thus, $H(K_1 \odot K_2)$ is the pull-back of $H(K_1 \otimes K_2)$ along the diagonal map. We will show the inclusions of $H(K_1 \odot K_2)$'s.

Theorem 7. *Let X_1 and X_2 be sets and let $K_{i,j} : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2$ be a kernel function for $i, j = 1, 2$. Assume that there exist some positive numbers c_j such that $K_{i,1} \leq c_i^2 K_{i,2}$ for $i = 1, 2$. Then $H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1}) \subset H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2})$ holds. Moreover, in this case, $\|f\|_{H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2})} \leq c_1 c_2 \|f\|_{H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1})}$ for all $f \in H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1})$.*

Proof. From Theorem 3, we see that $K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1} \leq c_1^2 c_2^2 K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2}$. From Theorem 4, we obtain the inclusion $H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1}) \subset H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2})$. Moreover, it is clear that the norm inequality $\|f\|_{H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2})} \leq c_1 c_2 \|f\|_{H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1})}$ holds for all $f \in H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1})$. \square

Corollary 8. *Let X_1 and X_2 be sets and let $K_{i,j} : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2$ be a kernel function for $i, j = 1, 2$. Assume that $H(K_{i,1}) \subset H(K_{i,2})$ for $i = 1, 2$. Then $H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1}) \subset H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2})$ holds.*

Proof. From Theorem 4, we see that kernel functions $K_{i,j}$ for $i, j = 1, 2$ satisfies the assumption in Theorem 7. Hence, we obtain the conclusion. \square

As a application of Theorem 3, we consider multipliers on the reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces of the form $H(K_1 \odot K_2)$.

Combining Theorems 3 and 6, we obtain the following result.

Corollary 9. *Let X be a set and let $K_{i,j} : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2$ be a kernel function for $i, j = 1, 2$. If there exists some constant $c_1 > 0$ such that $K_{1,1}(x, y) \leq c_1^2 K_{1,2}(x, y)$ and $f \in \mathcal{M}(H(K_{2,1}), H(H_{2,2}))$, then $f \in \mathcal{M}(H(K_{1,1} \odot K_{2,1}), H(K_{1,2} \odot K_{2,2}))$.*

Proof. Since f is a multiply of $H(K_{2,1})$ into $H(H_{2,2})$, there exists some constant $c_2 > 0$ such that

$$f(x)K_{2,1}(x, y)\overline{f(y)} \leq c_2^2 K_{2,2}(x, y).$$

by Theorem 6. By Theorem 3, we have

$$f(x)K_{1,1}(x, y)K_{2,1}(x, y)\overline{f(y)} \leq c_1^2 c_2^2 K_{1,2}(x, y)K_{2,2}(x, y)$$

as kernel functions. Again by Theorem 6, we obtain the conclusion. \square

Next, we study Hilbert spaces inside the Hardy space such as the range of $C_\varphi(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2}$.

Theorem 10. *Let φ and u be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{D}}$. The operator range $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u) = \mathcal{M}(C_\varphi(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2})$ is the reproducing kernel Hilbert space with kernel*

$$\frac{1 - \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)} u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)} \varphi(z)}.$$

Proof. Since the operator range $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)$ is contained boundedly to the Hardy space H^2 , $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)$ is the reproducing kernel Hilbert space.

Let K_λ^u be the kernel function for the functional on $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)$ of evaluation at λ . We have

$$\begin{aligned} K_\lambda^u(z) &= \langle K_\lambda^u, k_z \rangle_{H^2} \\ &= \langle K_\lambda^u, C_\varphi(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})C_\varphi^* k_z \rangle_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)} \\ &= \langle K_\lambda^u, C_\varphi(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})k_{\varphi(z)} \rangle_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)} \\ &= \langle K_\lambda^u, C_\varphi(1 - \overline{u(\varphi(z))}u)k_{\varphi(z)} \rangle_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)} \\ &= \langle C_\varphi(1 - \overline{u(\varphi(z))}u)k_{\varphi(z)}, K_\lambda^u \rangle_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)} \\ &= \frac{1 - \overline{u(\varphi(z))}u(\varphi(\lambda))}{1 - \overline{\varphi(z)}\varphi(\lambda)} \\ &= \frac{1 - \overline{u(\varphi(\lambda))}u(\varphi(z))}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

In [4, 9], the reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces with kernel K_λ^u are studied. In particular, we see from Theorem 1.1 in [9] that the kernel function $K_\lambda^u(z)$ is positive semi-definite. We note that, for any $f \in \mathcal{H}(u)$, the $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)$ -norm of $C_\varphi f$ is equal to $\mathcal{H}(u)$ -norm of f . Indeed, choose $g \in H^2 \ominus \text{Ker}(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2}$ such that $f = (I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2} g$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_\varphi f\|_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)}^2 &= \|C_\varphi (I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2} g\|_{C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u)}^2 \\ &= \|g\|_{H^2}^2 \\ &= \|(I - T_u T_{\bar{u}})^{1/2} g\|_{\mathcal{H}(u)}^2 \\ &= \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}(u)}^2. \end{aligned}$$

3 Main results

Before stating our statements, we need the following theorem as can be seen in [7].

Theorem 11 ([7]). *Let $X_i, i = 1, 2$ be sets, $\varphi : X_1 \rightarrow X_2$ a function and $K_i : X_i \times X_i \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2$ kernel functions. Then the following are equivalent:*

- (i) $\{f \circ \varphi : f \in \mathcal{H}(K_2)\} \subseteq \mathcal{H}(K_1)$;
- (ii) $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(K_2) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(K_1)$ is a bounded, linear operator;
- (iii) there exists a constant c such that $K_2(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) \leq c^2 K_1(x, y)$.

Moreover, in this case, $\|C_\varphi\|$ is the least such constant c .

Now we state our main results.

Theorem 12. *Let u and φ be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{D}}$ with $\varphi(0) = 0$. Then the composition operator $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(u) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(u \circ \varphi)$ is well-defined and bounded.*

Proof. First, we consider the de Branges-Rovnyak space $\mathcal{H}(\varphi)$. The assumption $\varphi(0) = 0$ guarantees the fact that constant functions belong to $\mathcal{H}(\varphi)$, since the reproducing kernel of $\mathcal{H}(\varphi)$ satisfies $k_0^{(\varphi)}(z) = 1$. Hence we have $\mathbb{C} \subset \mathcal{H}(\varphi)$. Therefore the inequality

$$\frac{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z} \geq 1$$

holds as kernel functions. Hence the Schur product theorem yields

$$\frac{1 - \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)} \leq \frac{1 - \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z}$$

From Theorems 11, the composition operator $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(u) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(u \circ \varphi)$ is well-defined and bounded. □

The condition $\varphi(0) = 0$ plays a crucial role in the proof of Theorem 12. Without this assumption, the boundedness of C_φ from $\mathcal{H}(u)$ to $\mathcal{H}(u \circ \varphi)$ may fail in general.

When u is an inner function, $\mathcal{H}(u)$ coincides with the model space $K_u = H^2 \ominus uH^2$. In this case, Theorem 12 recovers the boundedness of composition operators between certain model spaces obtained in [3, Section 6], showing that our result can be viewed as a natural extension of the model space theory to the setting of de Branges–Rovnyak spaces.

Theorem 13. *Let u, φ and ψ be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{D}}$. Then the composition operator $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(u) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(\psi u \circ \varphi)$ is well-defined and bounded.*

Proof. We have

$$\frac{1 - \overline{\psi(\lambda)u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}\psi(z)u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z} - \frac{1 - \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z} = \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u \circ \varphi(z) \frac{1 - \overline{\psi(\lambda)}\psi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z}$$

From the Schur product theorem, this is positive semi-definite. Thus, we obtain the inequality

$$\frac{1 - \overline{\psi(\lambda)u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}\psi(z)u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \bar{\lambda}z} \geq \frac{1 - \overline{u \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)}$$

as kernel functions. From Theorems 11, we conclude that $C_\varphi \mathcal{H}(u) \subset \mathcal{H}(\psi u \circ \varphi)$, that is, the composition operator $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(u) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(\psi u \circ \varphi)$ is well-defined and bounded. \square

Theorem 13 shows that the boundedness of C_φ can be preserved under multiplication of the symbol $u \circ \varphi$ by an arbitrary Schur function ψ . This phenomenon reflects the stability of de Branges–Rovnyak spaces under kernel domination and highlights the flexibility of the reproducing kernel approach adopted in this paper.

From Theorem 13, it is clear that Corollary 14 holds. Corollary 14 below is generalization of Corollary 6.6 in [3].

Corollary 14. *Let u and φ be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{D}}$. Then the composition operator $C_\varphi : \mathcal{H}(u) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(zu \circ \varphi)$ is well-defined and bounded.*

Next, we present some examples.

Example 15. (i) *The composition operator*

$$C_{z^2} : \mathcal{H}\left(\frac{1}{2}(1+z)\right) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}\left(\frac{1}{2}(i+z)(i-z)\right)$$

is well-defined and bounded.

(ii) *The composition operator*

$$C_{(-z)} : \mathcal{H}\left(\frac{1}{2}(1+z)\right) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}\left(\frac{1}{2}(1-z)\right)$$

is well-defined and bounded.

The above examples illustrate that the boundedness of composition operators on de Branges–Rovnyak spaces can be effectively studied via kernel inequalities. From the reproducing kernel viewpoint, the action of a composition operator corresponds to a pullback of kernels. It is therefore natural to ask whether the same method applies to weighted composition operators, where an additional multiplication by a bounded analytic function is involved. This motivates the study of weighted composition operators on de Branges–Rovnyak spaces in the next section.

4 Weighted composition operators

From the reproducing kernel perspective, composition operators and weighted composition operators share a common structural feature: both induce transformations of reproducing kernels governed by pullbacks and Schur products. Thus, the framework developed in Sections 2 and 3 naturally extends to the weighted setting, leading to boundedness results for weighted composition operators on de Branges–Rovnyak spaces.

Let φ be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \mathbb{D}$ and let ψ be in H^∞ . We define weighted composition operator $W_{\psi,\varphi}$ by $W_{\psi,\varphi}f = \psi f \circ \varphi$. If $\varphi(z) = z$, then $W_{\psi,\varphi}$ is the multiplication operator defined by ψ . If $\psi(z) = 1$, then $W_{\psi,\varphi}$ is the composition operator C_φ . In this section, we study the weighted composition operators on the de Branges–Rovnyak spaces by using the technique of the reproducing kernels. Before stating Theorem 16, The same argument as Theorem 10 shows that the operator range $W_{\psi,\varphi}\mathcal{H}(u_2) = \mathcal{M}(W_{\psi,\varphi}(I - T_{u_2}T_{\overline{u_2}})^{1/2})$ is the reproducing kernel Hilbert space with kernel

$$\overline{\psi(\lambda)}\psi(z)\frac{1 - \overline{u_2 \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u_2 \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)}.$$

The assumption in Theorem 16 expresses that the reproducing kernel of $\mathcal{H}(u_2 \circ \varphi)$ is dominated by that of $\mathcal{H}(u_1)$, which allows the weighted composition operator to act boundedly between the corresponding spaces.

Theorem 16. *Let u_1, u_2 and φ be in $\mathcal{S} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{D}}$ and ψ be in H^∞ . If*

$$1 - u_1(z)\overline{u_1(\lambda)} \geq 1 - u_2 \circ \varphi(z)\overline{u_2 \circ \varphi(\lambda)} \geq 0$$

as kernel functions, then the weighted composition operator $W_{\psi,\varphi} : \mathcal{H}(u_2) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(u_1)$ is a bounded linear operator.

Proof. Put $M = \sup\{|\psi(z)| : z \in \mathbb{D}\}$. From the assumption and Proposition 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} M^2 \cdot \frac{1 + |\varphi(0)|}{1 - |\varphi(0)|} \cdot \frac{1 - \overline{u_1(\lambda)}u_1(z)}{1 - \overline{\lambda}z} &\geq M^2 \cdot \frac{1 - \overline{u_2 \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u_2 \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)} \\ &\geq \overline{\psi(\lambda)}\psi(z) \frac{1 - \overline{u_2 \circ \varphi(\lambda)}u_2 \circ \varphi(z)}{1 - \overline{\varphi(\lambda)}\varphi(z)} \end{aligned}$$

as kernel functions.

From Theorem 7, we conclude that $W_{\psi,\varphi}H(u_2) \subset \mathcal{H}(u_1)$ and that the weighted composition operator $W_{\psi,\varphi} : \mathcal{H}(u_2) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}(u_1)$ is well-defined and bounded. \square

From the reproducing kernel viewpoint, the weighted composition operator $W_{\psi,\varphi}$ can be interpreted as a combination of a pullback and a Schur multiplication. This structural interpretation explains why the kernel domination techniques developed in the previous sections extend naturally to the weighted setting. In particular, Theorem 16 may be viewed as an extension of results due to Jury [5] on weighted composition operators acting on de Branges–Rovnyak spaces, formulated here within a unified kernel-based framework.

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